

Unmasking the Selfie Obsession: A Study on Dark Triad Personality Traits and Selfitis among University Students

Fariha Zehra Rani

Senior Instructor, Department of Psychiatry & Behavior Sciences, Baqai Medial University

Dr. Azra Shaheen

Associate Professor, Department of Psychiatry & Behavior Sciences, Baqai Medial University

ABSTRACT: The present research is directed to evaluate the connection between dark triad personality traits and selfitis behavior among undergraduates. A sample of 150 university students (females =75 and males =75) from different departments of clinical sciences and social sciences with age ranges from 18 to 25 years were included. Initially, a consent form was administered, followed by a Demographic form, Selfitis Behavior Scale (Balakrishnan & Griffiths, 2017), and a Short Dark Triad Scale (Jones & Paulhus, 2011). The cross-sectional design was utilized to sightsee the variables. At first, correlation was done to acquire the relationship of variables. In addition, regression was used to measure the projecting bond of dark triad personality traits with Selfitis Behavior. Statistical package for social sciences (SPSS) was used for the evaluation of responses. The outcome of existing research suggests a significant association between dark personality traits and selfitis behavior. Descriptive analysis revealed significant associations between selfitis behavior and two sub-scales of the Dark Triad (e.g., narcissism and psychopathy), whereas the association with the Machiavellianism sub-scale was not significant.

Keywords: Selfitis behavior, Machiavellianism, Narcissism, Psychopathy

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1. Introduction

Many aspects of life have changed with technological transformation. It has been found that 70% of the world population uses mobile devices, out of which 65% use smartphones. Similarly, statistical studies show that around 4 billion people are active on social networking platforms (Perez et al., 2023). The trend of selfies has become a central topic for many researches due to its excessive use. Furthermore, the typical behavior of taking and posting selfies has been reported as self-inflammation. In addition to that American Psychological Association has explained “Selfitis” as an obsessive urge to take and post selfies and grouped it into three categories namely; Borderline, Acute, and Chronic (Monacis et al., 2020). Another research on selfitis revealed that it is a real mental

condition where one feels the need to keep posting photographs of themselves on social media (Haque, 2020).

Findings of Selfitis further hyped the topic and led researchers to link it with different variables such as age, gender, and a variety of maladaptive behaviors and aversive personality traits such as Dark Triad personality traits. The “Dark Triad” was formerly envisioned by Paulhus and colleagues (2002) as an assemblage of three personality variables that are abstractly diverse but overlay empirically (Phulpoto, Oad, & Imran, 2024). Further, they described a dark triad framework in three social aversion traits (i.e., narcissism, Machiavellianism, and psychopathy).

Research on the correlation between selfitis behavior and the Short Dark Triad personality traits among university students has shown interesting findings. A study on Italian participants revealed that narcissism and psychopathy were positively associated with social media addiction through selfitis behavior, while Machiavellianism showed no direct relationship with either selfitis behavior or social media addiction (Monacis et al., 2020). Additionally, a study on Polish university students found a positive correlation between narcissism and health behaviors, particularly in students with lower levels of this trait, suggesting that narcissism may be linked to pro-health behaviors. According to Pearlman (2013), selfies are a mode of self-promoting activity that manifests “social media-driven narcissism”. The act of taking selfies, therefore, is one way for people to promote themselves to gain admiration from others and to feed their inflated self-views (Ertürk, 2016).

In Pakistan, selfitis behavior is associated with different psychological factors such as narcissism, self-esteem and social validation. It was reported that high levels of narcissism and low self-esteem can encourage selfitis behavior in young adults of the country as a way to gain validation from their surroundings (Dhillon, 2019). In terms of gender, Malik et al., (2020) it was stated that females were more prone to engage in selfie taking behavior as compared to males which is explained by females’ natural desire for social acceptance and trying to fulfill cultural expectations. Social media networking sites has further encouraged selfitis behavior, especially with their features like likes and comments which gives individuals a sense of satisfaction and dopamine rush, Lamba et al., (2016) stated that these features works as a positive reinforcement leading to individuals wanting to keep updating their profiles and stay active. Selfitis and psychological drives motivating such behavior i.e., narcissism, Machiavellianism, and psychopathy can have a significantly negative impact on an individual’s mental health and lead to problems like anxiety, depression and body dysmorphic features. Findings suggest that students who were actively engaged in selfitis behavior and sharing them showed increased levels anxiousness and depressive symptoms (Malik et al., (2020).

Significance of studying Dark Triad personality traits and Selfitis behavior has become essential due to its high comorbidity with technology related mental health issues commonly in younger adults (Bukhari, et al., 2024). Number of reports emerged in domestic and global means in 2014 proclaiming “selfitis” an obsession with capturing photographs was classified as a mental disorder. The present investigation aims to study the relationship between selfitis behaviors and the dark triad personality traits and how they motivate such

behavior so that effective and suitable interventions and awareness campaigns can be designed, and mental health of our youth can be taken care of (Imran, Zaidi, & Rehan, 2024).

2. Literature Review

There have been researches on selfitis behavior as well as dark triad personality traits Machiavellianism, and psychopathy, however, very few researches have studied the association between the two, especially incorporating the Pakistani context. The current study aims to contribute findings on the correlation of the two variables for better understanding and solutions (Ahmad, Bibi, & Imran, 2023).

Selfies and narcissism can be associated with each other due to the core nature of the need for societal validation and appreciation. Selfies are one of the tactics narcissists use to gain positive attention from the people around them and to promote themselves. Similarly a research conducted by Boursier et al., (2020) reveals that university-going students who indicated a higher level of narcissism engaged in selfie-taking behavior more frequently than other students to be admired and gain social acknowledgment. Additionally, a research conducted on men showed that men who were more active on social media and posted many selfies indicated higher levels of narcissism suggesting a strong and positive association between narcissistic tendencies and selfie-taking behavior (Sorokowski et al., 2015). A longitudinal study revealed a bidirectional association between selfies and narcissism; it stated that narcissistic individuals are more likely to capture selfies, however, individuals taking frequent selfies can also develop narcissistic tendencies (Halpern et al., 2016).

Regarding Machiavellianism, selfies are used more strategically rather than just as a means of social admiration and validation (Khosro, et al., 2024). Such individuals use selfies to paint a portrait, or a persona related to any agendas they might have so that they can influence and take advantage of others. Kircaburun and Griffiths (2018) reported that individuals with Machiavellian traits were engaging in high levels of selfie-taking behavior for manipulative purposes and presented themselves in a more desirable light. It was highlighted by a study that individuals who scored higher in Machiavellianism traits on dark triad qualities participated in selfitis behavior more frequently to gain attention and control their social presence and image (Balakrishnan & Griffiths, 2018).

Psychopathy does not seem to be directly associated with selfitis behavior as it is more likely to revolve around impulsive and un-empathetic behavior (Bukhari, et al., 2024). Psychopathic individuals might be engaging in selfie-taking behavior to show brazenness and fearlessness. Morino et al., (2018) suggested that an individual with psychopathic behavior can have a diverse range of motivations to engage in selfitis behavior, unlike individuals with other dark triad trait tendencies. Balakrishnan and Griffiths (2018) stated in their study that participants who scored high in psychopathy exhibited high levels of selfitis behavior which can be explained by their innate desire for stimulation and seeking attention. Other findings indicated that psychopathic individuals can be more active on social media and engage in selfie-taking practices due to their impulsivity and a way to seek thrill (Fox & Rooney, 2015).

Bousier et al., (2020) reported that out of all the dark triad personality traits, narcissism was the strongest predictor of selfitis behavior among young adults. Followed by Machiavellianism and finally psychopathy is an indirect motivator of selfitis behavior and is mediated by other variables. Malik and Rehman (2020) outlined in their study that social media addiction was a mediating factor between selfitis behavior and dark triad personality traits, especially mediating the association between narcissism and selfitis stating the habitual use of social media can lead to increased selfitis behavior in university students especially with narcissistic traits. When the current variables were further researched with a focus on Pakistan, a literature gap and limited findings were observed hence highlighting the need for the current study.

3. Research Method

Research Design

This study was quantitative and used a cross-sectional research design.

Population of the study

The study was conducted among university students. Students who participated were from various universities of Karachi majoring in social and clinical sciences.

Sample

A sample size of 150 university students from which N=75 females and N=75 males were included. Participants included were enrolled in undergraduate programs from different departments of clinical sciences and social sciences of Karachi. The respondents' age was 18 to 25 years with a mean age of 21.70 (SD=1.446) years.

Sampling Technique

The convenient sampling method was used to collect the data for this exploration.

Inclusion and Exclusion

Participants between the age ranges of 18 to 25 years and enrolled in undergraduate programs of HEC-recognized universities were included. Married participants and respondents with clinical disorders and/or physical illnesses were excluded.

Instrument

Demographic Sheet

The demographic profile for this study was a self-developed questionnaire and contained information related to age, gender, education, marital status, birth order, total number of siblings, socio-economic status, family structure, parent's education and occupation, and family's monthly income as per judgment of participants.

Short Dark Triad (SD3)

Short Dark Triad (SD3) was developed by Jones and Paulhus (2014) to assess the dark triad of personality traits. It comprises three sub-scales (Machiavellianism, Narcissism,

and Psychopathy) and contains 27 items, 9 items each measuring the specific personality traits. The scale has a five-point Likert rating system where 1 represents “disagree strongly” and 5 indicates “agree strongly” with five reverse-scored items in the scale as well.

Selfitis Behavior Scale (SBS)

Selfitis Behavior Scale (SBS) was used to measure the selfitis behavior of the current sample. The scale was introduced by Griffiths and Balakrishnan (2018). The SBS comprises of 20 items and six sub-scale categories (i.e. environmental enhancement, self-confidence, mood modification, social competition, attention seeking, and social conformity). The scale has a five-point Likert scoring system in which 1 indicates “strongly agree”, and 5 as “strongly disagree”. The lowest possible score of SBS is 20 and the highest possible score is 100. Scores ranges of the Selfitis behavior scale is 20 to 100 where 20 to 40 indicates the lowest possible, 41 to 60 mild selfitis behavior, 61 to 80 moderate selfitis behavior, and 81 to 100 marked level of selfitis behavior. Overall reliability of the scale was 0.88 and the Cronbach’s alpha was 0.60.

Procedure

Participants were approached individually or in groups (up to 15 people) through a convenient sampling technique. The students who participated in this study were from various HEC-recognized universities in Karachi, Pakistan. Participants were briefed on the nature and purpose of the study. All ethical considerations were taken into consideration during the study. Respondents were ensured about the confidentiality of their information; they were debriefed about the nature and purpose of the research. To safeguard ethical values, individual consent was obtained from each participant. After their consent, the Demographic Form, Selfitis Behavior Scale (SBS), and Short Dark Triad (SD3) were administered. Additionally, to reduce the possibility of incomplete information, the measures were thoroughly checked before collecting information from participants. Each participant to complete the survey took approximately 30-45 minutes to complete. Lastly, respondents were acknowledged for their cooperation and time.

Statistical Analysis Plan

The information collected was analyzed using IBM SPSS, V-25. The data collected were scored according to the scale’s standard scoring rubrics. To analyze the data in statistical terms, Pearson Correlation and regression analysis were used to assess the predictive relationship of the Dark Triad personality traits to selfitis behavior.

Ethical Considerations

Formal approval was obtained from the Departmental Research Committee and the Advanced Study and Research Board (A.S.R.B) of the University of Karachi before conducting the study. The research was conducted in a manner that does not compromise the respect, dignity, rights, and well-being of the participants. Participants were briefed on the nature and purpose of the study. Their identities and the information they provide are kept confidential.

4. Results

For result formulation, Descriptive statistics of frequencies, percentages, and means of demographic variables such as age, gender, socioeconomic status, family structure, academic performance, birth order, and parental occupation were calculated. To analyze the association of selfitis behavior scale with the Dark Triad of personality Pearson product-moment correlation and Linear regression analysis were used.

Descriptive Statistics

Table No 1: Demographic Profile of the Participants

Variables		F	%
Birth Order	First	43	28.7%
	Middle	73	48.7%
	Last	34	22.7%
Socioeconomic Status	Middle	112	74.7%
	Upper Middle	38	25.3%
	Upper class	0	0
Family Structure	Joint	106	70.7%
	Nuclear	44	29.3%
Academic Grades	A+	22	14.7%
	A	109	72.7%
	B+	5	3.3%
	B	14	9.3%
Father's Occupation	Non-Working	4	2.7%
	Government Employee	28	18.7%
	Private Employee	118	78.7%
Mother's Occupation	Non-Working	120	80.0%
	Government Employee	2	1.3%
	Private Employee	28	18.7%
Sample age	(M=21.70, SD=1.446)		

Note. f= Frequency, %= Percentage, M= Mean, SD=Standard Deviation

The table 1 revealed the results of the demographic sheet using frequency distribution. The mean age of participants was (M=21.70 and SD=1.446). The table of frequencies and percentages indicates that 109 out of 150 have an above-grade academic performance 74.7 % of students belong to the middle class and 70.7% belong to a joint family setup.

Hypothesis Testing

Table No 2: Linear Regression of Machiavellianism (trait of Dark Triad Personality) with Selfitis Behavior (N=150)

R ²	Adj. R ²	F	Sig
.005	-.00	.72	.395

P<0.01** p<0.05*

The table 2 of linear regression analysis indicates an insignificant relation between Machiavellianism, a Dark triad personality trait with selfitis behavior scale [$R=.070$, $R^2=.005$ and $p>.05$]

Table No 3: Linear Regression of Narcissism (trait of Dark Triad Personality) with Selfitis Behavior (N=150)

R2	Adj. R²	F	Sig
.08	.07	13.22	.000

P<0.01** p<0.05*

The table 3 of linear regression analysis indicates a significant positive relation between Narcissism with selfitis behavior scale [$R=.286$, $R^2=.082$ and $p>.05$].

Table No 4: Linear Regression of Psychopathy (trait of Dark Triad Personality) with Selfitis Behavior (N=150)

R2	Adj. R²	F	Sig
.10	.09	16.76	.000

P<0.01** p<0.05*

The table 4 of the linear regression analysis indicates significant positive relation between the Psychopathy of Dark triad personality with selfitis behavior scale [$R=.319$, $df=148$ and $p<.05$].

5. Discussion

A significant positive relationship was observed between narcissism and selfitis behavior in the present which is in line with the previous literature. Narcissistic tendencies and persistent selfie-taking behavior are consistently linked with each other as such individuals use selfies to showcase themselves and gain attention from their surroundings. Sorokowski et al. (2015) reported a positive and significant association between narcissism and selfitis, more frequently observed in males. The relationship between narcissism and selfies can be explained by low levels of self-esteem in an individual as highlighted by Budge (2020) who indicated that people use selfies to gain external recognition. A study conducted in Pakistan revealed similar findings, 200 participants between the ages of 16 to 24 years were observed and it was found that high levels of narcissistic tendencies were strongly associated with clicking selfies as a way of feeling a higher level of self-esteem (Malik et al., 2020).

The present research observed an insignificant relationship between Machiavellianism and selfitis behavior which is a trend that has been observed in some previous research as well. Past studies have aimed to study the dark triad personality traits as a motivator in selfie-taking behavior however Machiavellianism was not noticed to be a significant predictor of it (Griffiths et al., 2020). Research conducted by Kircaburun and

colleagues (2018) aimed to find out if persistent use of social media mediated the correlation between dark triad characteristics and selfitis behavior and findings suggested an insignificant association between Machiavellianism and selfie-taking practices indicating the individuals do not engage in taking selfies to manipulate others for personal advantage. However, Abbas et al. (2019) highlighted that as Pakistan's population has been increasing and a rising trend of social media usage and addiction is observed, it is important that further investigations are done on the trait of Machiavellianism and how it can motivate individuals to engage in selfitis behavior.

The final trait of the dark triad i.e., psychopathy is characterized by individuals exhibiting impulsive and risky behavior, self-interest, and lack of regard for rules and regulations and others was indicated to have a significant positive association with selfitis behavior in the current study. This could be explained by the need for attention and recognition of such individuals which motivates them to post selfies on social media. Balakrishnan and Griffiths (2018) who were the developers of the Selfitis Behavior Scale reported that individuals who acquired high scores in the psychopathy measure were more prone to engage in selfitis behavior with underlying motivations to gain admiration of others and participate in perceived social competition. In the research mentioned above which investigated the mediating role of social media addiction between selfitis behavior and dark triad personality traits, indicated a significant positive correlation between psychopathy and engagement in social media practices i.e., selfie-taking (Griffiths et al., 2020) which aligns with the findings of the present research. Khan et al. (2017) reported in their findings that individuals with psychopathic tendencies are more likely to engage in selfitis as a way to control social perception and recognition while having a lack of emotional connection, this practice is encouraged by the Pakistani culture where social standing holds immense importance.

Many findings suggest that a portion of university students engage in some kind of risky and narcissistic selfie-taking behavior, with males being more frequent (Kaur et al., 2020). Similarly, a study conducted in Pakistan stated that both males and females with high narcissism exhibited selfitis, especially males (Dhillon, 2019). However further investigation needs to be conducted on the relationship between Machiavellianism, psychopathy, and selfitis behavior in males and females to conclude. The present study is consistent with the previous literature and presses on the need to focus on the mental health of university students and their activities so that effective measures can be implemented.

6. Conclusion

The present study provided links between dark Triad personality traits with selfitis behaviors among university students of Karachi Pakistan. The current findings suggest that Narcissism and Psychopathy of Dark triad personality are associated with selfitis behavior whereas has an insignificant association with Machiavellianism. Since there are very limited studies on selfitis behavior and dark triad behavior in Pakistani students the present research can help shed light on this evolving issue and therefore promote well-being among people.

7. Limitations and Recommendations

One of the limitations of the current research is the limited sample size. A significant result may be found on all variables if a larger sample size has been used and findings can be generalized. As the data has been taken from university students, considering the sensitivity of topic responses bias could exist and muddle research findings. Further, the effect can be also produced due to student's sensitivity towards evaluation. Further investigation must be done on the current topic with a larger sample size. The impact of gender differences and cultural factors should be studied in more detail for better insight.

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